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The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) wishes to thank all the reviewers for their intellectual contributions by timely reviewing manuscripts, and supporting the journal's vision of "*Enriching Beautiful Minds towards Intelligent Minds*".

From the desk of the Editor-in-Chief, the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) would like to thank all the reviewers who made it possible to publish this volume, Volume 6, Issue 2, November 2022.

Merry Christmas and Happy New Year 2023 in Advance

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

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